

Listen Local Collaboration Guide

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Short Introduction

Listen Local is an open collaboration for artists, fans, managers, developers to provide alternatives to connect local audiences with local artists through locally relevant music recommendations and findings. As a project of the Digital Music Observatory it aims to make big data work for small labels and self-released artists, and to make algorithms work for and not against them.

This Collaboration Manual is created for the existing and future contributors of this project. You can download the latest version of the manual from listen-local-collaboration.dataobservatory.eu. The last authoritative copy of this manual (Version 2022-06-06) is doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6617137.

[Listen Local Project Page](#) - Powered by the [Digital Music Observatory](#) See the [FAQ](#) after [checking already open questions](#)

Trustworthy Information

All good music should find its audience. Local ecosystems, such as shops, events must find ways to play local music, introduce visitors to local artists, and make sure that some of the royalty payments (for example, paid by restaurants or bars) stays in the local music ecosystem. When somebody is shopping in Milan for fashion, in the shops some music from Milan and its regions should be played.

Listen Local facilitates the best human-human and human-computer interactions, and makes sure that machine learning algorithms do not learn from bad information, leading to bad recommendations, and unsuccessful artist placements and low valuation and appreciation for their music.

The Listen Local Databases are location-specific and subjective databases about artists and their works. Listen Local Slovakia contains artists and music references that are relevant in the context of Slovakia: the music is made in Slovakia, or the artists or music relates to the Slovak language and culture. Listen Local Gent is music relevant in the city of Gent.

- [2 The Write-In Databases](#) contain only publicly and legally available information collected and organized by the Listen Local Collaboration with the oversight of local music curators. The write-in databases contains information that our automated systems with the oversight of our curators write into them. For example, the Slovak Comprehensive Music Database contains music that our Slovak music curators subjectively think to be Slovak music in one way or another. Our curators use a sound and consistent set of criteria to write in music and artists into our databases, but they maintain their subjective and professional judgement.
- [3 The Opt-In Databases](#) contain information that creator of the music provided about herself. The opt-in databases consist of two datasets: a closed and GDPR protected personal identification dataset and a public dataset that contains information released with the consent of the creator. Any artists can opt into our databases pending curatorial approval. (An artist can opt-in into the Slovak Comprehensive Database if he or she feels Slovak, pending the judgement of the curator that the inclusion of the artists will be relevant for music audiences and users looking for Slovak music.) Any artist can opt-out from the personal dataset without curatorial approval.

- **3.2** Any artist can **opt-out** from the personal dataset without curatorial approval. Special rules apply on **deceased** artists—partly, because GDPR no longer applies, partly, because identity will be relevant for new generations. For example, the classical work of Franz Liszt lived and worked in the Austro-Hungarian Empire, and his work may be credibly claimed by the audiences and researchers of Slovak (he worked much in the current Slovak capital of Bratislava), Hungarian (his place of birth) or the music heritage of the city of Weimar in Germany. The inclusion of his work Weimar, Hungary (very likely) or Japan (unlikely) specific datasets requires the judgement of our curators.

The principles of the Listen Local system were outlined in the [Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad](#). This study was supported by the Slovak Arts Council and the state51 music group, and it is available in both English and Slovak languages¹.

Participate

Listen Local is a highly automated system that uses open-source algorithms for automation and open, trustworthy AI. We deploy these technologies to help humans to work with music, enjoy music and participate in music. Keeping in mind a basic principle of ethical, trustworthy AI, our system is always maintaining human agency and oversight.

- **7 Curators** are the most important collaborators to make Listen Local human-centered and ethical. They manage the write-in database and ensure that the automated systems collect and store correct information about artists and their music. To maintain ongoing data ownership of artists, they manage the opt-in and opt-out procedures for artists.

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¹Slovak version: (Antal, 2020b), English version: (Antal, 2020a).

Chapter 1

Listen Local

Listen Local is an open collaboration for artists, fans, managers, developers to provide alternatives to connect local audiences with local artists through locally relevant music recommendations and findings. As a project of the Digital Music Observatory it aims to make big data work for small labels and self-released artists, and to make algorithms work for and not against them.

1.1 Listen Local Goals

Listen Local is a highly automated system that uses open-source algorithms for automation and open, trustworthy AI. We deploy these technologies to help humans to work with music, enjoy music and participate in music. Keeping in mind a basic principle of ethical, trustworthy AI, our system is always maintaining human agency and oversight.

1.2 Listen Local Milestones

- 2019: The Slovak Music Industry Report specifies the need for new instruments that help the diversity of music recommendation and discovery in digital streaming.
- 2020: The principles of the Listen Local system were outlined in the [Feasibility Study On Promoting Slovak Music In Slovakia & Abroad](#). This study was supported by the Slovak Arts Council and the state51 music group, and it is available in both English and Slovak languages¹.
- 2021: JUMP Music Market Accelerator
- 2022: TAS
- 2022. 06.03. MusicAIRE grant for Listen Local Lithuania managed by [MXF](#).
- 2022. 06.xx. Cooperation agreement with [Faniak](#).

¹Slovak version: ([Antal, 2020b](#)), English version: ([Antal, 2020a](#)).

Chapter 2

The Write-In Databases

The write-in databases are subjective, because they contain only publicly, and legally available information collected and organized by the Listen Local Collaboration with the oversight of local music curators. The write-in database of Listen Local Slovakia contains music that our Slovak music curators think to be Slovak music in one way or another.

Chapter 3

The Opt-in Databases

The opt-in databases contain information that creator of the music provided about herself. The opt-in databases consist of two datasets: a closed and GDPR protected personal identification dataset and a public dataset that contains information released with the consent of the creator. Any artists can opt into our databases pending curatorial approval. (An artist can opt-in into the Slovak Comprehensive Database if he or she feels Slovak, pending the judgement of the curator that the inclusion of the artists will be relevant for music audiences and users looking for Slovak music.)

Any artist can [opt-out](#) from the personal dataset without curatorial approval. Special rules apply on [deceased](#) artists.

3.1 Write-in: Getting Started with a new Listen Local Dataset

1. Start with a Spotify playlist. Add artists that are relevant to your playlist. Please check out a starting playlist [Listen Local Utrecht](#).
2. Each playlist should be organized according to a location (how?)
3. Let Reprex's Listen Local system create the initial write-in database.
4. Review the database in Google Spreadsheet.

3.1.1 How location matters?

3.2 Opt-out Procedure

Our opt-out procedure is always open for an artists who no longer wants to identify with one of our databases.

- Removal from the Opt-In Datasets requires no justification: these datasets contain information that fall under personal data protection rules.
- Removal from the Write-in Datasets requires a justification and pending curatorial decision.

To give a hypothetical—and rather unlikely—scenario, an artist may inform Listen Local that she no longer identifies with Slovakia and wants to be deleted from the Slovak Comprehensive Music Database. We will immediately remove her from the Opt-in Datasets. However, if her music is widely perceived

by audiences, musicologist, or local content regulation as Slovak, we may keep her work in the write-in datasets, clearly stating in the biographical information that the artists do not identify ‘Slovak’.

A more likely case is that an artist is featured in a city-specific dataset in Gent, but he moves to San Francisco. The curator of the Gent dataset may feel that the artist left a large footprint in the music of Gent and list his work in Listen Local Gent, however, we may transfer the Opt-In (more personal data) to Listen Local SF and in the future keep including the work of the artists in San Francisco—especially new work made in the new city.

3.3 Deceased Artists

The music work of deceased artists has valuable copyrights and neighboring rights for many decades ahead. The heir of a Slovak composer may have an interest in making sure that people looking for Slovak music find it in the future. The opt-in procedure is therefore open for the heirs of deceased artists, pending curatorial judgement about the suitability of including the artist and her work into any of our databases.

The opt-out procedure is open for the heirs if they can prove that the deceased artists explicitly wished to opt-out while still living. GDPR and many other rights do not apply for deceased people. Personal identification is a personal decision, and deceased people can no longer speak for themselves.

Chapter 4

Use cases

Listen Local is an open collaboration for artists, fans, managers, developers to provide alternatives to connect local audiences with local artists through locally relevant music recommendations and findings. As a project of the Digital Music Observatory it aims to make big data work for small labels and self-released artists, and to make algorithms work for and not against them.

Chapter 5

Artists

Listen Local is an open collaboration for artists, fans, managers, developers to provide alternatives to connect local audiences with local artists through locally relevant music recommendations and findings. As a project of the Digital Music Observatory it aims to make big data work for small labels and self-released artists, and to make algorithms work for and not against them.

Chapter 6

Music & Lyrics

Listen Local is an open collaboration for artists, fans, managers, developers to provide alternatives to connect local audiences with local artists through locally relevant music recommendations and findings. As a project of the Digital Music Observatory it aims to make big data work for small labels and self-released artists, and to make algorithms work for and not against them.

Chapter 7

Curators

Curators are the most important collaborators to make Listen Local human-centered and ethical. They manage the write-in database and ensure that the automated systems collect and store correct information about artists and their music. To maintain ongoing data ownership of artists, they manage the opt-in and opt-out procedures for artists.

Our music curators play an essential role in making sure that big data works for all, including self-released artists and independent labels. Their work facilitates the best human-human and human-computer interactions, and makes sure that machine learning algorithms do not learn from bad information, leading to bad recommendations, and unsuccessful artist placements and low valuation and appreciation for their music.

7.1 How to become a curator?

You can become a curator by invitation to the project, or by applying in a short letter.

Your simplified resumé and profile picture. Take a look at profile of [Dominika Semaňáková](#), our first Listen Local curator. We will need the same information from you, and a profile picture that is at least 500px wide (jpg or png format.)

Links and Identifiers You can optionally attach to your profile your LinkedIn profile, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube channel, Spotify Creator account, or anything that you use as a music professional—select at least one where artists can get in touch with you. Furthermore, for contributions to this project, we will need the following three identifiers from you: - **ORCID** Your ORCID ID, which will enable us to unambiguously attribute your contribution to Listen Local. ORCID is used in open science and other publishing to unambiguously attribute copyrights to a person. It takes a few minutes to register an account if you do not have it yet. We will attribute your name and ORCID ID on all assets that you contribute to. - **Github account ID** Our project management dashboard and the FAQ is on Github, and all our source files will be versioned on Github. Github is the most popular open collaboration platform for open source software editors. If you do not write code, you will not contribute to our source files, but with a Github id you ask questions, take on tasks and report them ready on our project dashboard. All contributors will be added as a contributor to the [dataobservatory-eu/listen-local-collaboration](#) repository. - **Spotify Account Link**: You must have a free or premium account on Spotify. We will ask playlists initially on Spotify for ease of collaboration. If you do not use Spotify, you can create a free account for your Listen Local contributions.

You must abide the **CONTRIBUTOR COVENANT CODE OF CONDUCT** pledging to make participation in our community a harassment-free experience for everyone, regardless of age, body size, visible or invisible disability, ethnicity, sex characteristics, gender identity and expression, level of experience,

education, socio-economic status, nationality, personal appearance, race, caste, color, religion, or sexual identity and orientation. (See [translations](#) and the [Contributor Covenant FAQ](#).)

New curators

See the [FAQ](#) after checking the already [open questions](#)

Digital Music Observatory

The [Digital Music Observatory](#) is a highly automated, open source, open data observatory that links public datasets in order to provide a comprehensive view of the European music industry. The DMO produces key business and policy indicators that enable the growth of music business strategies and national music policies in a way that works both for music lover audiences and the creative enterprises of the sector, and contributes to a more competitive, fair and sustainable European music ecosystem.

Reprex

Listen Local is a project within the Digital Music Observatory.

It was a project initiated by [CEEMID](#), a predecessor of Reprex. The first project of Listen Local was **Listen Local Slovakia** in partnership with [SOZA](#) and the *state51 music group*.

CEEMID

SOZA

Listen Local Slovakia was a project initiated by [SOZA](#), [CEEMID](#) and the *state51 music group* and supported by the Slovak Arts Council. **SOZA** is a founding partner of the Digital Music Observatory and its predecessor, [CEEMID](#).

The **Slovak Performing and Mechanical Rights Society** (**SOZA**), executes international standards on copyright protection in the territory of the Slovak Republic. **SOZA** does not only represent local authors in Slovakia, but also all foreign authors from those countries where CMOs concluded an Agreement on Reciprocal Representation. **SOZA** represents rightsholders— authors, sub-authors, music arrangers and authors of written part of the work, i.e. lyrics, libretto, as well as publishers of those works. On their behalf **SOZA** monitors the use of musical works in the territory of the Slovak Republic, collects royalties and at the same time provides administrative, economic and legal services.

MXF - Muzikos eksporto fondas

MXF curates **Listen Local Lithuania**. **MXF - Muzikos eksporto fondas** is a non-profit NGO with charitable status founded in 2015, working on projects to develop the music and nightlife sectors in Lithuania. **MXF** also runs [Vilnius Night Alliance](#), an initiative to unite socially responsible venues, bookers, and artists under a code of ethics, representing their interests at local and national government level. This gives **MXF** access to a wide variety of businesses and musicians in Lithuania and high visibility in the entertainment and hospitality sectors. **Vilnius Night Alliance** is known worldwide as an innovator in campaigning for responsible and sustainable nightlife development.

Music Export Ukraine

Artist Bridge

Frequently Asked Questions

[See the FAQ](#) after [checking already open questions](#)

You need a [Github account ID](#) to write questions to the FAQ, or to contribute to our source files and assets. All contributors will be added as a contributor to the [dataobservatory-eu/listen-local-collaboration](#) repository.

APPENDIX

Bibliography

Antal, D. (2020a). Feasibility study on promoting slovak music in slovakia & abroad.

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